

Battery-based hybrid power stations for non-interconnected islands in Greece

Dimitrios Zafirakis^{*a}, Georgios Tzanes^a, Georgios Nomikos^a, John Kaldellis^a, Zisimos Mantas^b, Konstantinos Kaousias^c

^aSoft Energy Applications and Environmental Protection Laboratory,

Faculty of Engineering, Mechanical Engineering Department, University of West Attica, Athens 12201, Greece

^bEunice Energy Group, Athens 10674, Greece

^cHellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator, Islands Network Operation Department, Athens 11741, Greece

*Corresponding author's mail: dzaf@teipir.gr

Abstract

Currently, non-interconnected islands (NIIs) around the globe rely mainly on oil-based power generation introducing high operational costs, especially for the smallest and most remote of islands. Owing to the existing thermal-based infrastructure, constraints on the development and operation of local renewable energy sources (RES) installations are often considerable due to the inherent inflexibility of similar electricity systems to facilitate high shares of variable RES power generation. This is reflected in RES shares that hardly exceed 15% in the local electricity fuel mix, even in the case of high-quality RES potential being available. At the same time, technological advancements and growth noted in the booming market of batteries drive down associated costs and pave the way for the development of hybrid RES and storage configurations which can address RES intermittency. Such schemes have been elaborated in depth during the last decade, with certain countries, like Greece, developing sophisticated regulations for the introduction of Hybrid Power Stations (HPSs) in NIIs. In this context, by examining two exemplary case studies, including a small and a large scale island system of the Aegean Sea, the current study aims to provide insights from the application of the Greek regulatory framework for HPSs in NIIs, focusing on battery-based configurations. In doing so, application results are discussed and conclusions are made with regards to the maturity of the local framework to encourage a massive introduction of similar HPSs in the local region.

Keywords: hybrid power stations; battery storage; regulatory framework; Aegean islands

1. Introduction

Despite the fact that renewable energy sources (RES) have reached grid parity for mainland / national grid applications, non-interconnected islands (NIIs) around the globe still rely heavily on oil-based power generation, introducing high operational costs, especially for the smallest and most remote of islands [1]. This is largely due to the fact that the existing thermal-based infrastructure, when initially designed, did not consider of the need to facilitate large shares of RES in the local electricity fuel mix. As such, there are significant constraints on the development and operation of local RES installations, linked with the inherent inflexibility of similar electricity systems to support high shares of variable RES power generation [2]. On the other hand, technological advancements noted in the booming market of batteries seem to drive down associated costs, thus gradually paving the way for the development of hybrid RES and storage configurations that can address the problem of RES intermittency. Such

schemes have been elaborated in depth during the last decade, with certain countries, like Greece, developing sophisticated regulations for the introduction of Hybrid Power Stations (HPSs) in NIIs, enabling the transition of local systems to potentially lower costs on the basis of local RES resources' optimal exploitation. In this context, by examining two exemplary case studies, including a small and a large scale island system of the Aegean Sea (i.e the island of Anafi and the island system of Fourni-Samos, Fig. 1), the current study aims to provide insights from the local regulatory framework of Greece regarding the operation of HPSs in NIIs.

Fig. 1: The islands of Anafi and Fourni-Samos in the Aegean

2. General principals of energy management in NIIs

Energy management principles applied in the context of the study are currently presented, in accordance with the Greek regulatory framework for HPSs and the Grid Code for NIIs [3]. To this end, the simulation code and software used (see also following paragraph) are able to reproduce the daily dispatch schedule and energy management for a NII comprising of dispatchable (thermal units and HPSs) and non-dispatchable units (wind and PV parks), considering at the same time the existing limitations such as the technical minima of the in-operation thermal units, the dynamic penetration limit for RES, the need to comply with spinning reserve requirements, etc [4]. With regards to the treatment of the different units in terms of control and dispatchability, the PV units are treated as if not accepting restrictions of their output while wind parks power injections to grid are subject to set points, which are defined after the consideration of the in-operation thermal units technical minima and the dynamic penetration limit, which is imposed by the local grid operator [5]. In reality, depending on the spatial dispersion of wind parks and the performance of employed forecasting algorithms [6], a certain percentage of the local wind energy generation can be considered as dispatchable, following the same norm with local PVs and thus further reducing the residual load available. The rest however is subject to curtailments.

Regarding HPSs, they are set to follow an intra-day dispatch schedule on the basis of day-ahead guaranteed energy offers submitted to the local Operator, separately for the first (00:00 to 12:00) and second (12:00 to 00:00) period of dispatch, considering the available energy stores together with an estimation of the day-ahead RES power generation profile. Such offers are received by the Operator that then proceeds to the issuance of the dispatch schedule that the HPS should comply with. It is noted at this point that the guaranteed energy amounts provided by the HPS allow also for the direct energy contribution from the RES components of the HPS, at a predefined, maximum level, that also relates to the response time of the storage system employed.

3. Internal operation of HPS, design constraints and remuneration principals

Focusing on the internal operation of the HPS, wind and/or PV power generation of the HPS can be exploited for a) charging the battery storage component of the HPS, b) contributing directly to the provision of guaranteed energy at a given level, c) delivering energy directly to the local grid, as stochastic RES generation, depending on the residual load available. To this end, two distinct periods are identified within the day, i.e. the hours of scheduled generation (in accordance with the dispatch schedule received from the Operator) and the hours of non-scheduled generation. During the hours of scheduled production, the wind power grid injections are prioritized (due to normally higher remuneration), with the secondary surplus (after satisfying the

schedule's requirements and after fully charged batteries) considered to be stochastic and subject to curtailments, thus exploited only in the case of residual load available. In case of insufficient wind and PV power generation (with respect to scheduled production), the remaining energy is covered via the storage system. During the hours of non-scheduled production, the sum of the wind and PV power generation is mainly used to charge the batteries, with any secondary surplus (after fully charging the batteries) considered to be stochastic.

Moreover, with regards to design constraints, it is noted that according to the regulation in force the maximum output of the HPS RES components is not allowed to exceed 120% of the charging power of the storage component of the HPS, while it is also necessary that a minimum 40% of the annual HPS RES generation is exploited for the reduction of thermal-based energy generation in the NII each time examined.

Concerning the remuneration of HPSs in NIIs, different cost components are identified, these including the guaranteed, the standard wind and PV, and the scheduled wind and PV energy tariffs (€/MWh). The first applies to the energy drawn from the HPS storage component and results as the max value of the operational cost of peak thermal units, of the base-load thermal units times 1.25, and of the reference tariff of wind parks times 1.5. The standard wind and PV energy tariffs are 98€/MWh and 1.1 times the previous year average wholesale price of the Greek mainland electricity system respectively. Those apply to the stochastic energy provided to the grid directly from RES, in the form of surplus. The scheduled wind and PV energy tariffs apply to the guaranteed energy provided to the grid directly from RES. These are configured as the average value of the guaranteed storage tariff and the standard wind and PV tariff respectively.

In addition, HPS remuneration includes the capacity credit (€/kW) which corresponds to the specific installation and fixed operational costs (for an indicative operation period of 20 years) of a new thermal power station of capacity equivalent to the HPS guaranteed power and to 8 hours of delivery of guaranteed power over the day. Any reduction in the daily period of guaranteed power delivery below 8 hours suggests a proportional reduction of the capacity credit.

4. The Microgrid Simulator

To facilitate the analysis of different scenarios for the introduction of HPSs in NIIs, a dedicated simulator has been developed [7] in the context of TILOS Horizon 2020 project in C# programming language, advancing previous work in the field [8] and being able to also look at the deployment of different energy management strategies, depending on the system topology each time considered. To this end, the Microgrid Simulator is able to cover the following scenarios:

- **Stand-alone** mode of operation for an island microgrid. In that case the given microgrid is treated as an island system and the aim of the Microgrid Simulator is to provide a different set of energy solutions considering increased shares of RES combined with energy storage,

DSM and zero or moderate diesel contribution examining the problem from the *grid operator point of view*.

- **Energy trade** mode of operation for an island microgrid interconnected to another island or the mainland, considering market signals for the energy management of the microgrid in relation to the host grid (equivalent of an electricity market). In that case the problem is examined from the *local community point of view* in order to explore the trade-off between energy autonomy and market participation for the given island microgrid [9].
- **Private HPS actor** mode of operation under the Greek regulation framework for RES-based HPSs. In that case, the Microgrid Simulator focuses on the operation of HPSs stations, following the principles of the regulatory framework in force for HPSs in Greek NIIs, examining the problem from the *private actor point of view*.

Currently, the private HPS actor mode of operation will be used and applied in two different islands of the Aegean Sea, i.e. the island of Anafi and the island system of Fourni-Samos.

5. Case study presentation and assumptions

Anafi is a very small scale island of the South Aegean, belonging to the complex of Cyclades (see also Fig. 1). The local population is close to 270 permanent inhabitants, which may even triple during the summer period, owing to the arrival of tourists. In terms of electricity supply, Anafi is not interconnected and as such, it covers its needs relying on the operation of a local thermal power station of 800kW. At the same time, the annual electricity consumption of the island reaches 1.36GWh and the respective peak load demand is close to 620kW, while till today, there is no RES capacity installed. As a result, the entire consumption is covered on the basis of oil-based power generation using exclusively diesel-oil, with the operational cost being 260€/MWh.

With regards to the local RES potential, the island appreciates excellent solar potential of 1800kWh/m².a at the horizontal plane, which suggests an annual CF of 22% at a tilt angle of 30° in combination with medium-high quality wind potential determined by an average wind speed of 8.7m/sec.

To this end, and given also the small size of the specific island system, the HPS examined for the case of Anafi comprises of a small scale wind turbine of 50kW (type L50-200, max power of 54.5kW), combined with a PV station also of 50kW (comprising of PV panels of 250W each) and a medium-sized lithium-ion battery system of 333kWh capacity and 100kW nominal output, altogether set to provide a guaranteed power output of 50kW. Considering a maximum depth of discharge (DoD) of 92%, the useful storage capacity of the battery corresponds to 306kWh, further reduced to 250kWh in order to also account for an emergency buffer. As such, the period of guaranteed power delivery for the given configuration is equivalent to 5 hours per day. At the same time, instantaneous contribution of RES to the provision of guaranteed power is determined at 50kW, i.e. 100% of the respective guaranteed output, which is justified on the basis of

the response time of the employed technology, and the non-scheduled generation period is set between 00:00 and 8:00am.

Fourni is a complex of almost twenty very small and small scale islands, located on the region of North Aegean (see also Fig. 1), with an overall population exceeding 1000 habitants. Fourni is interconnected to the bigger-scale, neighboring island of Samos, where from it is supplied with electricity via a subsea cable. As such, Fourni are essentially a part of the Samos electricity system, with the latter concentrating a permanent population of over 30.000 habitants. To this end, the electricity consumption of the Fourni-Samos system reaches ~147GWh, with the respective annual peak demand exceeding 32MW and with the respective load curve presenting a smoother year-round profile in comparison with Anafi. With regards to the local electricity capacity, a heavy oil-fired power station of ~50MW is operated in Samos at a cost of 100€/MWh. At the same time, there is a total of six wind parks on Samos with an overall capacity of 8.375MW, operating at an average CF of 28% (over the actual wind energy exploited), while existing PV installations reach 4.37MW, with the respective max permitted capacity being 5.32MW [10]. The broader area appreciates medium-high quality solar potential (i.e. 1715kWh/m².a at the tilted plane of 30°), while the local wind potential is determined by an average wind speed of 9.3m/sec.

In this context, a bigger scale HPS, than the one of Anafi, is examined for the case of Fourni-Samos, comprising of a 900kW Enercon E-44 wind turbine (max power of 910kW), a 90kW PV station (with the same PV panels as for Anafi) and a lithium-ion battery system of 1330kWh/1000kW, set to offer a guaranteed power of 250kW (DoD 92%, 224kWh emergency buffer). To this end, the period of guaranteed power delivery is equivalent to 4 hours per day, while the instantaneous contribution of RES components to the provision of guaranteed power is set to 100% of the respective guaranteed output, i.e. 250kW, again justified on the basis of the employed batteries' response time. Finally, the period of non-scheduled generation is set between 00:00 and 6:00am.

6. Application results

Using the Microgrid Simulator and the required input data concerning the examined HPSs components and the electricity systems of Anafi and Fourni-Samos, the main application results of the simulations carried out for the above HPS configurations are discussed in the following paragraphs. In this context, in Fig. 2, the hourly fuel mix of Anafi is presented for two consecutive weeks during summer (1-14/8), considering introduction of the examined HPS and also full coverage of the max permitted PV capacity of 46.26kW, without however any additional wind turbines/farms. The dispatch of the local thermal units is further analyzed, see also Fig. 3, where the cumulative technical minima of the latter are also given. In this context, although dispatch of a single unit is normally sufficient during the winter period, due to the

increase of demand, dispatch of all four units is necessary during the respective summer period.

Fig. 2: Summer period fuel mix analysis for the island of Anafi with the contribution of the examined HPS

Fig. 3: Summer period thermal units' dispatch and resulting technical minima for the island of Anafi

The internal energy balance of the HPS during summer is next analyzed in Fig. 4, demonstrating the delivery of guaranteed energy blocks in comparison to the RES production variation, the battery state of charge (the useful energy storage capacity is illustrated) and the absorption or rejection of any resulting RES surplus, with the latter however being more considerable during the winter period, i.e. when the low levels of demand do not allow for the increased absorption of the appearing RES surplus. This is more clearly illustrated in Fig. 5, where the appearing wind and PV surplus is broken down to its absorbed and rejected parts, in relation to the respective residual load of the system maximizing during summer and thus allowing the absorption of the appearing RES surplus almost entirely. To this end, over 65% of the wind turbine's generated energy is used to support delivery of guaranteed energy to the grid and battery operation (charging and auxiliaries) over the year, with the rest ~1/3 corresponding to excess energy that is curtailed by 25% and absorbed by 8%. The distribution of the available PV energy generation is quite similar, with PV curtailments again reaching 25%.

With regards to the remuneration of the energy delivered to the local grid, the values of Table 1 are adopted for each of the

remuneration components of the HPS, considering also that the cost of energy absorbed from the local grid in order to cover any energy deficit with regards to the auxiliaries of the battery storage is equal to the production cost of local base load units.

Table 1: Remuneration and cost components' values

Remuneration/cost component	Anafi	Fourni-Samos
Peak production cost (€/MWh)	263	98
Base-load production cost (€/MWh)	256	92
HPS battery (guar.) tariff (€/MWh)	320	147
HPS wind (stoch.) tariff (€/MWh)	98	98
HPS PV (stoch.) tariff (€/MWh)	60.15	60.15
HPS wind (guar.) tariff (€/MWh)	209	122.5
HPS PV (guar.) tariff (€/MWh)	190	103.6
New th. station investment (€/kW)	81.5	116.5
New th. station fixed O&M (€/kW)	48.5	48.5
HPS capacity credit (€/kW.a)	130	165

Fig. 4: Summer period energy balance analysis for the examined Anafi HPS

Fig. 5: Winter period analysis for the absorption/rejection of the stochastic RES surplus from the examined Anafi HPS

To this end, the associated net operational revenues reflect the importance of the battery part due to both the high tariff of 320€/MWh and the respective share of contribution in the delivery of guaranteed energy, which is similar to the respective wind-based (see also Fig. 6). On the other hand, the

capacity credit may be determined as moderate, with the overall net annual revenues estimated in the order of 45k€, without however considering of any maintenance costs.

Fig. 6: Net annual operational revenues of the Anafi HPS

Similar to the case of Anafi, application results for the case of Fourni-Samos and examined HPS are next discussed. More precisely, the in operation wind parks of Fourni-Samos cover a significant part of load demand, while contribution of the examined HPS is as expected negligible (due to its size). Concerning the internal balance analysis of the HPS, the curtailments of the accruing RES surplus can be illustrated in the graph of Fig. 7, with the appearing residual load of the local electricity system limiting the absorption of RES surplus.

Fig. 7: Winter period analysis for the absorption/rejection of the HPS RES surplus from the examined Fourni-Samos

In this context, it is more than 50% and 30% of the HPS wind and PV energy production respectively that is being curtailed over the year, designating that the local electricity system is saturated in terms of existing RES, which also hinders the efficient operation of the HPS. The absorbed part of the excess RES production on the other hand is 11% and 9.5% for the wind turbine and PV park respectively, while in terms of direct RES contribution to the delivery of guaranteed energy, the corresponding numbers are 28% and 45%, with the rest used for battery charging and battery auxiliaries.

Next, as far as the remuneration of the energy delivered to the local grid is concerned, the associated net operational

revenues are given in Fig. 8, per main component, reflecting the importance of the wind energy part, mainly due to the size of the wind turbine employed. The capacity credit is again considered to be moderate, while the contribution of the battery component is reduced, owing also to the reduced period of non-scheduled generation, resulting to net annual revenues of ~215k€ for the HPS of Fourni-Samos.

Figure 8: Net annual operational revenues of the Fourni-Samos HPS

7. Discussion - Conclusions

Insights from the application of the Greek regulatory framework on HPSs for NIIs were provided in the current study, using two representative case studies for a small and big scale island system of the Aegean Sea. The first case concerned the island of Anafi, standing as a small-scale NII (peak demand of ~620kW) of increased operating costs, due to the use also of diesel oil, presenting inconsiderable RES infrastructure. An HPS of 100kW RES capacity and 333kWh of battery storage was tested, with the guaranteed power set at 50kW, equivalent to ~1/3 of the local average hourly load demand of ~155kW and to 50% of the HPS RES capacity. The second case on the other hand concerned a big-scale electricity system of more than 32MW of peak demand, with an hourly average load of ~17MW over the year and with the HPS configuration examined being in the range of a price-taker unit, i.e. 1MW of RES capacity and 1330kWh of storage, offering a guaranteed output of 250kW which is equivalent to only 1.5% of the average hourly load of the Fourni-Samos system and 25% of the HPS RES capacity. Opposite to the case of Anafi however, the Fourni-Samos electricity system presents significant RES capacity, reflected by the in operation RES of more than ~12.5MW. Moreover, both the battery capacity selected for the two island cases, which suggests "tight" HPS configurations with 5 and 4 hours of guaranteed power autonomy respectively, and the period of scheduled generation extended to cover the biggest part of the day, imply a RES-following approach that aims to the maximum exploitation of the HPS RES generation under minimum battery investment costs. In this context, and according to the application results obtained, the main challenge identified for

the given set of case studies relates to the trade-off between increased RES curtailments and extra battery storage capacity, the latter also allowing for higher guaranteed power outputs.

All things equal, the already aggravated -in terms of RES curtailments- system of Fourni-Samos seems to not facilitate effectively the introduction of RES-following HPSs, although the more or less balanced load demand profile of the island system supports the better exploitation of the HPS yield year round. The opposite is true for the case of Anafi, where the considerably lower winter load demand imposes significant curtailments, further aggravated by the inflexibility of local thermal units (4x200kW) and relevant technical minima. On the other hand, the absence of local wind parks suggests increased residual load exploited for the absorption of wind energy surplus, which ameliorates the situation on an annual basis. At the same time, increased operating costs due to the use of diesel oil justify increased HPS tariffs for Anafi, while heavy oil use and economies of scale reduce thermal-based generation costs considerably for the case of Fourni-Samos, which also impacts the remuneration of the HPS.

8. Conclusions

To conclude, according to the results obtained, there is indication that bigger scale islands, hosting also significant RES, cannot easily facilitate the introduction of RES-following HPSs with reduced storage capacity. At the same time, and owing to the lower operating costs of local thermal power stations, the storage component for such applications should be of reasonable cost, which, for the time being at least, seems to rule out batteries and encourage for the examination of large-scale storage solutions such as PHS. The above do not apply in the case that expensive solutions, such as gas turbines using diesel-oil, are used for peak demand shaving in similar systems, which could in turn justify the introduction of small scale, high-tariff HPSs, dedicated to the replacement of the former. The situation for small scale islands with inconsiderable RES capacity is as expected more favorable, with the increased operating costs of thermal units encouraging also the examination of battery-based HPSs. On the other hand, inflexibility of the local fleet of thermal units and the reduced load demand during the winter period also pose challenges in the proper sizing and design of a HPS.

Abbreviations

DoD: Depth of Discharge
HPS: Hybrid Power Station
NII: Non-Interconnected Island
PV: Photovoltaic
RES: Renewable Energy Sources

References

[1] Kaldellis, J.K., Zafirakis, D. (2007) Present situation and future prospects of electricity generation in Aegean Archipelago islands. *Energy policy*. 35, 4623-4639.

[2] Kaldellis, J.K. (2008) The wind potential impact on the maximum wind energy penetration in autonomous electrical grids. *Renewable energy*. 33, 1665-1677.

[3] Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator S.A. (2018) Grid Code for Non-Interconnected Islands. 2nd ed, Available at: <https://www.deddie.gr/> (in Greek)

[4] Psarros, G.N., Nanou, S.I., Papaefthymiou, S.V., Papathanassiou S.A. (2018) Generation scheduling in non-interconnected islands with high RES penetration. *Renewable energy*. 115, 338-352.

[5] Katsaprakakis, D.A. (2016) Hybrid power plants in non-interconnected insular systems. *Applied energy*. 164, 268-283.

[6] Alamo, D.H., Medina, R.N., Ruano, S.D., García, S.S., Moustris, K., Kavadias, K., Zafirakis, D., Tzanes, G., Zafeiraki, E., Spyropoulos, G., Kaldellis, J.K., Notton, G., Duchaud, J.L., Nivet, M.L., Fouilloy, A., Lespinats, S. (2018) An Advanced Forecasting System for the Optimum Energy Management of Island Microgrids. *Applied Energy Symposium and Forum, REM2018: Renewable Energy Integration with Mini/Microgrid*, 28-30 September 2018, Rhodes, Greece.

[7] Zafirakis, D., Tzanes, G., Kaldellis, J.K. (2017) An advanced microgrid simulator for stand-alone and market-dependent energy strategies. *2017 IEEE International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering and 2017 IEEE Industrial and Commercial Power Systems Europe (EEEIC / I&CPS Europe)*, 6-9 June 2017, Milan, Italy.

[8] Tzanes, G.T., Zafirakis, D., Papapostolou, C., Kavadias, K., Kaldellis, J.K. (2017) PHAROS: An Integrated Planning Tool for Meeting the Energy and Water Needs of Remote Islands using RES-based Hybrid Solutions. *Energy procedia*. 142, 2586-2591.

[9] Wu, L., Ortmeyer, T., Li, J. (2016) The community microgrid distribution system of the future. *Electricity journal*. 29, 16-21.

[10] Greek Regulatory Authority for Energy (2017) Decision on the maximum capacity of dispatchable and non-dispatchable RES units in NIIs.

Acknowledgement

This study was supported from TILOS project (Horizon 2020 Low Carbon Energy Local / small-scale storage LCE-08-2014). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 646529.

